

Note on the impact of meteorological data from PIRATA moorings on global weather forecasts

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Updated 15/10/2018 to include more assimilation cycles and to cover longer time period. As a result, numerical results differ as compared to initial estimation.

1. Introduction

To assess the impact of observations on weather forecasts, a common approach is to withdraw them from the assimilation, and conduct Observing System Experiments. This requires dedicated and costly numerical experiments. Such experiments are regularly conducted to inform observing system operators and data assimilators, and serve to guide the evolutions of the Global Observing System and of global data assimilation systems.

For instance, the 6th workshop on the impact of various observing systems (Sato and Riishojgaard, 2016) reviewed the latest results in this field. Another approach, also reported at that workshop, is to consider sensitivity metrics.

For example, the operational ECMWF system computes the individual Forecast Sensitivity to Observation (FSO; Cardinali, 2009) and stores it in the Observation Feedback Archive (OFA). The present note analyses the FSO results found for PIRATA buoys.

The outline of the note is as follows. Data and methodology are presented in section 2. Results are shown and discussed in section 3. The last section proposes conclusions.

2. Data and methodology

The observations considered here are those assimilated by the ECMWF high-resolution operational numerical weather prediction system between May 2015 and April 2018, for 216 assimilation cycles (typically days 1, 10, and 20 in each month, and two assimilation cycles per day). However, for 3 assimilation cycles, the OFA was not available, so in total 213 assimilation cycles were considered, retaining all the observations assimilated. They can be grouped in four main categories:

- surface observations over sea (buoys, ships),
- surface observations over land
- upper-air observations (radiosondes, aircraft, profilers),
- satellite observations (sounders, ocean scatterometers, radio occultation, ozone, atmospheric motion vectors, ...).

For PIRATA buoys, the following identifiers are retained: 13001* (12°N 23°W), 13002 (21°N 23°W), 13008* (15°N 38°W), 13009 (8°N 38°W), 13010 (0°N 0°E), 15001* (10°S 10°W), 15002 (0°N 10°W), 15006 (6°S 10°W), 15007* (6°S 8°E), 31001 (0°N 35°W), 31002* (4°N 38°W), 31003 (8°S

30°W), 31004 (14°S 32°W), 31005* (19°S 34°W), 31006 (4°N 23°W), 31007* (0°N 23°W), 41026 (12°N 38°W), 41139* (20°N 38°W). Buoys with functioning barometers are indicated with a star. For the other buoys, only the wind observation was assimilated.

The FSO is stored within the observation feedback, for each assimilated observation. The FSO has a unit of J/kg and it is an extensive quantity (the magnitude is additive for subsystems). The computations are hence straightforward (sums).

3. Results

Considering the total number of observations assimilated operationally by ECMWF, the contributions, in decreasing order, are from satellites, upper-air (radiosondes, aircraft), land-surface, and sea-surface. The contribution of each category is shown in a pie chart in Fig. 1a. The numbers of sea-surface observations are not even visible on the pie chart below, indicating that these observations are in much fewer numbers than other observing systems.

Figure 1 : Number of observations and total FSO

However, if one considers the contribution of observations to improving the forecasts (by reduction of the 24-hour forecast error *via* the data assimilation), one finds a different picture. Figure 1b suggests that the share of sea-surface observations in the total impact is actually much larger than the share of these observations in the total numbers. Surface marine observations are responsible for about 3.5 % of the total forecast error reduction at 24 hours.

If one investigates further to select individual platforms, the PIRATA moored buoys, on average, contribute, in the ECMWF operational data assimilation and prediction system:

- 0.00045 (\pm 0.00013) % of the total number of observations assimilated,

- 0.00352 (± 0.00729) % of the total 24-hour global error forecast reduction.

The uncertainty indicated in parentheses is the robust standard deviation over the distribution. It is estimated as the median absolute deviation over the distribution, multiplied by 1.482580 (NIST definition).

An impact factor can be computed as the inverse ratio between the two quantities above. This impact factor for PIRATA observations is around **7.8 if one computes the ratio of these average numbers**. However, one must note that the two quantities that form the ratio show large variations (as the number of observations assimilated by a single network is rather small). **Consequently, the average ratio is more informative, as the underlying ratios fluctuate largely, at 10.4 (± 17.3).**

This ratio is less than for the average of drifting buoys (reporting only surface pressure) in the vicinity, at **16.0 (± 19.0)**, or less than for the average of drifting buoys on the surface of the globe, at **34.8 (± 12.5)**, noting that most drifters are located away from the Tropics. This result is consistent with the meteorological expectation that observations of synoptic meteorology (such as pressure) contain comparatively less information on the general circulation near the Equator than in the mid-latitudes.

However, this number still exceeds that obtained for many other components of the global observing system. For comparison, over the same time period and in the same global prediction system:

- the impact factor for surface marine observations other than buoys is **4.75 (± 3.34)**;
- the impact factor for surface land-based observing systems is **3.97 (± 1.08)**;
- the impact factor for upper-air observing systems (including aircraft and radiosondes) is **2.03 (± 0.24)**;
- the impact factor for satellites is **0.79 (± 0.04)**.

The impact factors reported here cover both surface pressure and wind. However, not all PIRATA buoys report surface pressure (only 8 buoys out of 18 do; see section 2). It can hence be interesting to separate the impact between surface pressure and wind components.

Parameter	Surface pressure	Zonal wind component	Meridional wind component
Number of observations	9934	18151	18151
Total FSO (J/kg)	-1678	-135	-238

Table 1: Results for the PIRATA buoys, separating by assimilated meteorological variable

Over all the days considered here, Table 1 indicates that the largest impact is from the surface pressure observations. For wind, the impact is much larger for the meridional component. This is expected as the wind circulation along this direction typically bears the largest variations in amplitude in this region. Compared to the number of observations, the impact of surface pressure observations stands out far more than that of wind observations.

As indicated above, the impact factor fluctuates with the number of observations and the impact these have in the reduction of forecast errors. Considering slow variations over time can be instructing. From one assimilation cycle to the next, the fluctuations are large, so quarterly averages are considered here.

Figure 2 : Timeseries of the 3-month average impact factor (note logarithmic vertical axis).

The impact factor fluctuates over time, with PIRATA moorings showing comparatively lower impact in the middle of 2017 than at other times. Interpreting these fluctuations is not straightforward and requires going back to the two quantities that form the ratio. Figure 3 shows that the number of observations has approximately been increasing over the time period (though there were fewer data in 2016). This may be because the moorings are progressively being replaced by new equipment (T-FLEX, with higher return rates).

Figure 3 also shows that the impact of the data has been more irregular in 2017, with several months when the impact featured an opposite sign. This is believed to be related to the type of weather conditions and forecast errors that these observations may have helped to observe and reduce (respectively).

Figure 3 : Timeseries (per month) of the total number of PIRATA observations assimilated (top) and the corresponding total FSO (bottom).

4. Conclusions

The results presented in this note suggest that the collection of meteorological data (pressure and wind) from buoys in the Tropical Atlantic delivers valuable benefits to global weather predictions.

In particular, the value of PIRATA observations stands out, at twice the value of surface marine observations other than buoys. The largest impact is actually obtained from surface pressure data, available from about only half the PIRATA buoys, suggesting that more barometers would be useful to yield even more impact on global NWP.

In future work, one could explore whether the results found here would still hold if a small number of PIRATA buoys were equipped with conventional barometers, as used in mid-latitudes, instead of the laboratory-grade barometers presently used on PIRATA buoys. Indeed, one must remind that the barometers used on drifters and deployed in the Tropical Atlantic are no different from those used in other latitudes, and yet their impact from this region is found to be highly beneficial.

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References

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